

Simulation Scaling in Nuclear Energy : Implementing Parallel Execution Framework for URANIE

Jacques David^{a*}, Vincent Bergeaud^b

^a CEA/DEN/SA2P, CEA-Saclay, 91191 , Gif sur Yvette, France

^b CEA/DEN/DM2S/LGLS, CEA-Saclay, 91191 , Gif sur Yvette, France

Abstract

Mathematical models, designed to simulate complex physics are use in scientific and engineering studies. In the case of nuclear applications, assessing safety parameter such as fuel temperature, numerical simulations is paramount, in order to gain confidence versus comparison to experience. The URANIE tool uses propagation methods to assess uncertainties in simulation output parameters in order to better evaluate confidence intervals (e.g., of temperature, pressure, etc.). This is used for Verification and Validation and Uncertainties Quantification (or VVUQ) process used for safety analysis.

While URANIE is well suited for launching many instances of serial codes, it suffers from a lack of scalability and portability when used for coupled simulations and/or parallel codes. The aim of the project is therefore to enhance this launching mechanism to support a wider variety of applications, leveraging on HPC capabilities to go further to a new level of statistical assessment for models.

1. Introduction

Uncertainty quantification and data assimilation are key to industrial acceptance of predictive simulations (cf. PRACE Scientific Case report [8]). URANIE has been developed as the working platform of choice in VVUQ for CEA, AREVA, EDF and other partners, leveraging open source tools such as CERN's ROOT toolkit [6] and EDF/CEA's integration platform SALOME [7], and included as a sub-part in open European projects of NUClear REactor SIMulation in 6th, 7th, now 8th framework (NURESIM, NURISP, NURES SAFE [10]). Others project using URANIE includes multi-criteria optimization for laser simulation (CELIA), and uses in ALLIANCES platform (ANDRA, French national waste storage agency).

URANIE is based on Root (Version v5.32), an object-oriented software multi-platform developed at CERN for particle physics concerns, more exactly for data analysis generated by LHC (Large Hadron Collider) (see [6] for more information). URANIE integrates a large amount of features enabled by Root and especially, a C++ interpreter, SQL databases access, visualisation tools and statistical analysis.

* Corresponding author *E-mail address*: jacques.david@cea.fr

URANIE distribution mechanism enables the user to leave the analysis script untouched regardless of the architecture on which it runs. It gives the possibility to mix together several levels of MPI-based parallelism: the numerical models used in the DOE can be serial codes, MPI-based parallel codes or simulations coupled via the SALOME framework [SALOME13].

The URANIE framework works by analyzing the environment variables in order to define a number of cores available for computation. The available cores are the used in order to distribute the simulation points according to the cores required for each computation (1 for serial codes, more for parallel computations or coupled computations).

Intrinsically parallel nature of the distribution of computations calls in theory for excellent performances in terms of scaling. However, the parallel performance is limited by the I/O pattern of the codes. The simultaneous execution of hundreds or thousands of simultaneous instances of the same code can lead to heavy loads for the I/O system, which can result in poor performance.

Another track for improvement is the placement of processes on a processor. When using simulations with SALOME framework, processes which encapsulate the code services are launched without MPI, therefore with no indication on the placement of the process on the processor. Therefore, processes often compete for CPU on the same core, leading to inefficient behaviour.

URANIE is built in a modular way with several libraries (Figure 1) devoted for a particular task in the Uncertainty and Sensitivity (US) analysis. In the article, we then describe main libraries of the platform.

Figure 1 : Functional diagram of URANIE

The main library defines the TDataServer object which contains all the information about the uncertain variables for the US analysis. Then, this TDataServer object flows through the other libraries in order to apply the methods of the study.

The second library, the Sampler library, is devoted to generate a design of experiment (deterministic/statistical) from characteristics of the uncertain variables. Several methodologies are implemented:

- qMC ("quasi Monte-Carlo") sequences (Sobol, Halton);
- SRS ("Simple Random Sampling"), LHS ("Latin Hypercube Sampling"), ROA ("Random Orthogonal Array"),

Archimedean Copulas;

- MCMC ("Markov Chain Monte-Carlo") method for Gaussian mixture.

The Launcher library is devoted to manage the computation on a PC (sequential) or on a cluster (distributed). The goal is to construct the Y matrix jointed in the X matrix of the design of experiment. We can launch either the original computation code or an analytical function as surrogate models. The surrogate models can be built by the modeler library or written by the user following a prototype.

The Modeler library is devoted to build a surrogate model from input to output attributes contained in a database. The surrogate models implemented in Uranie are polynomial, polynomial Chaos expansion and neural networks. We plan to implement the kriging methodology soon. After building the surrogate model, it can be saved in several languages like C/C++, FORTRAN, PMML ("Predictive Model Markup Language" is the leading XML standard for save statistical and data mining models) for using it in the US analysis instead of the computation code with a very low CPU time computation.

The Reliability library is devoted to perform a reliability analysis. At present time, this library is not implemented, but we plan to implement the SORM/FORM methodology. The optimizer library is devoted to perform a Verification and Validation code or to find the optimum of a computation code or analytical function. We can also perform multi-criteria optimization with Genetic Algorithms. The goal of the UncertModeler library is to examine how well a sample of data agrees with a given distribution as its population with goodness-of-fit techniques.

The last library, the Sensitivity library, contains several methods to make the sensitivity analysis between the two X and Y matrix like Regression method (Pearson, Spearman), Screening method (Morris) and Sobol indexes (Sobol's methodologies, FAST).

ROOT (and therefore URANIE) has a C++ interpreter which allows us to integrate easily new algorithms or to customize complex treatment with several objects in a function with few parameters. The C++ interpreter is the first level of the user interface. The second level user interface is an XML file; this file contains the description of the uncertain variables and the different steps to apply for US analysis. The XML interface allows us to integrate easily Uranie modules in an industrial platform.

2. Workplan and strategy

In order to efficiently address HPC usage, some bottlenecks must be addressed, with main goal to get to scalability and performance on large scale (> n x 1000s cores) computers. Starting since 2013, URANIE is capable of running inside SALOME framework, which has been ported successfully onto small and medium clusters, and must now be tailored to much larger HPC supercomputer capabilities. The approaches to be applied have being studied within PRACE-2IP "Emerging applications" PA type C [5] with goal to enhance MPI parallelization on either single code or multiple (à la "ensemble") simulations.

URANIE is based on the realization of DOEs (Design Of Experiments), i.e. a set of simulations in which the same code is executed with slight modifications in the input files, so that the uncertainty range of the input variables is covered (see general architecture in figure 2).

Figure 2 : general architecture of URANIE generic launching process

In order to accommodate various middlewares and launch codes as black boxes, the URANIE launcher has initially the following strategy:

- a single job is allocated,
- the master node runs a control process,
- the control process launches children of the control process, each child running an mpirun script which runs one computation in the DOE,
- the control process checks for the state of the children in order to decide when to run new children.

This strategy gives good flexibility and good performance on dozen to hundreds of processors, but the bottleneck on the master node can become a problem for large runs. Also, this strategy gives little control on the placement of processes in the context of coupled simulations. Work was then started aimed at improving URANIE on two issues:

- Capacity to launch efficiently large DOEs
- Capacity to provide checkpoint/restart mechanisms for large DOEs that were incompletely run.

A careful analysis of the software architecture was performed during 2-IP PA, especially directed at these key libraries:

- DataServer library, which defines the TDataServer object which contains all the information about the uncertain variables for the analyses;
- Sampler library, which is devoted to generate a design of experiment (deterministic/statistical) from characteristics of the uncertain variables. Several methodologies are implemented:
 - qMC ("quasi Monte-Carlo") sequences (Sobol, Halton);
 - SRS ("Simple Random Sampling"), LHS ("Latin Hypercube Sampling"), ROA ("Random Orthogonal Array"), Archimedean Copulas;
 - MCMC ("Markov Chain Monte-Carlo") method for Gaussian mixture.
- Launcher library, which is devoted to manage the computation on a desktop (sequential) or on a cluster (distributed). The goal is to construct the Y matrix jointed in the X matrix of the design of experiment;
- Modeler library, which is devoted to build a surrogate model from input to output attributes contained in a database;
- Optimizer library, which is devoted to perform a Verification and Validation code or to find the optimum of a computation code or analytical function

Although significant forward (porting) steps were made in this first work, new ideas had then to be found for larger scalability on the curie-class machine (with goal of hundred to thousands, even ten of thousands processors). Main objectives are listed as follows :

- To have the same source script whether launching on a local cluster or on a Tier-0 class machine,
- Keep same called code (model implementation)
- Be able to launch with similar ease
 - sequential simulations,
 - scripts,
 - coupled simulation within SALOME-YACS,
 - parallel simulation
- Make the system reach a good scalability,
- Maintain robustness,
- Be able to still analyze (partial) results even in case some executions fail,
- Be able to relaunch (restart) the "experiment plan" for completing it, in case of previous time-limit.

Three strategy are then considered :

- Strategy #1 : have parallelism at the level of system process-launching (fork/threads, ...) :
the **TLauncher::run()** primitive
- Strategy #2 : have parallelism at the level of (native) batch system, **slurm** in the case of **curie** :
the **TLauncherByStep::run("curie")** primitive
- Strategy #3 : have parallelism at the level of MPI parallel (supposedly portable) launching :
the **TRelauncher::run()** primitive

We have to keep in mind that one difficulty is that mpi is not reentrant, that is, mpirun cannot call itself.

For strategy #1, the prerequisite is to have one job in which all computation are hosted. Then the aim is to be able to run Desing of Experiments :

- On serial codes
- On MPI-based parallel codes
- On coupled simulations (with SALOME platform or with MPI)

Then, in that case the implementation is (see figure 2) :

- The master node manages the distribution of computations as processors become available
- When a processor group becomes available, the master process is forked and runs mpirun
- The end of the job execution is detected by analyzing the state of the child process

Figure 3 : Strategy #1 implementation

The 2nd and 3rd strategy are based on a direct “batch” parallelism for the launcher, differing only by mechanism : the **slurm** mechanism for strategy #2, native on **curie**, and the **mpirun** mechanism for strategy #3.

For *slurm-based strategy #2*, work has been done with direct support on TGCC application support team (Bruno Frogé et alii). The implementation calls for using a particular launching mode, embedded in slurm, that enable to associate a specific list on nodes to a computation run, and then to launch more (sub-)computation that there are available nodes (for this job) :

```
ccc_mprun -E '-exclusive' -np 2 my_launch_MPI.exe &
```

This has been encapsulated in URANIE 3.4 as the **TLauncherByStep::run()** primitive

For *mpirun-based strategy #3*, encapsulated in URANIE as the **TRelauncherByStep::run()** primitive, the concept is much more

standard, to have one master core that is the controlling supervisor for the n-1 others cores that will execute computations. This gives a good scalability and a good robustness, but is less generic – we have to modify the user code in order to be able to launch experimental designs with inner (MPI) parallelism.

3. Results

Two experiments have been done on the **flowrate** “toy” code (see [9], p35). The **flowrate** code computes rate of flow from an aquifer through a borehole, with an analytical function for its inside kernel, so it is the usual code of choice for URANIE training in VVUQ for physicists [11]. The first experiment was involving a number of jobs equal to the number of allocated cores; this is a straightforward set-up. On the second one, the number of jobs was doubled, in order to enable better compute resources usage by some over-allocation. In both experiments, the output files have a limited size (a few thousands of bytes). The number of cores was doubled incrementally from 16 to 2048.

On the first experiment, the scalability is good for all three strategies up to 512 cores; it degrades for the SLURM based one beyond that number.

Figure 4 : **straightforward** njobs=ncores (weak scalability) performance for the three strategies (time in mm, so lower is better)

The second experiment shows the limits of the two first strategies which are based on scheduling on the master node via system-level mechanisms: they require heavy scheduling tasks to define which jobs have stopped and which should be restarted. In that respect, the SLURM based one is more robust than strategy #1. MPI-based strategy which involves message passing for scheduling is much more robust and efficient for this test case, achieving very good scalability up to 2048 nodes.

Figure 5 : **over-allocation** njobs=2*ncores (weak scalability) performance for the three strategies (time in mm, lower is better).
Missing points denote computations that did not complete (time-limit).

Further experiments with larger output files suggest that the key factor to the limitation of the scalability is the intensity of the I/O workload.

It should be noted that these results are based on the execution of a serial code. Strategies #1 and #2 offer the possibility to launch jobs for which each individual computation point is itself an MPI-based computation, while this is not possible with strategy #3 without modifying the code. Therefore, the usage of URANIE on “blackbox” MPI-based codes is achieved with strategies #1 and #2 only.

A summary comparison can be made, showing that depending on the application and on the machine configuration, each

strategy can be useful :

	Strategy 1 system multiprocessing primitives	Strategy 2 slurm based primitives	Strategy 3 mpirun based primitives
Scalability	+ (for ncores = njobs)	++	+++
Robustness	++	++	+++
Genericity	+++	++ Limited to slurm-based batch systems	+ Directly usable on sequential jobs, but Need modification work for parallel sub-codes (not yet available for “XML” mode)

4. Summary and outlook

A porting of URANIE framework from cluster-class to large-scale (Tier-0like) class computational resource was done, and different strategies were studied in order to test scalability, robustness and genericity of the framework. Leveraging on previous 2-IP framework, three parallelization control strategies were studied and implemented, with help of the Tier-0 application support team. The strategy #3, “mpi-master” version, performs best, but is not completely generic : it requires some work to be done on sub-applications (the problem being that it must be done for each new sub-app), because of the “mpi under mpi” curse.

Whereas work on the improvement of strategy 1 has already been performed in the frame of a PRACE-2IP collaboration between PSNC and CEA [12], and as SLURM based strategy is being studied in collaboration with CURIE support team, work remains to be done to continue the amelioration of the platform, notably in the process of I/O tuning, restarting/completing of the “design of experiments” when it is not completed in one job (and so hits time-limit), and performance tuning vs process placement on sophisticated multi-core architecture. While this is to push forward, URANIE will be reinforced as an Open-Source platform of choice for Verification, Validation, and Uncertainties Quantification in major physics disciplines, including Fluid Mechanics, Mechanics, and others, such as used in enhanced nuclear safety analysis and validation.

Acknowledgements

This work was financially supported by the PRACE project funded in part by the EUs 7th Framework Programme (FP7/2007-2013) under grant agreement no. RI-312763. The work was achieved using the PRACE Research Infrastructure Tier0 system curie, CEA, France, as well as the local resources of CEA at the same place (airain system).

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